

ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ALTERNATIVE FEEDING METHOD ON HUNGER SATISFACTION AND ANTHROPOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS AMONG INFANTS WITH CLEFT LIP AND CLEFT PALATE AT SAVEETHA MEDICAL COLLEGE AND HOSPITAL AT CHENNAI

Dr. Mary Minolin. T¹

Professor, HOD of Child Health Nursing, Saveetha College of Nursing, SIMATS, Thandalam, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.
minolinbabu@gmail.com

Jeevitha. K²

M.Sc Nursing II year, Saveetha College of Nursing, SIMATS, Thandalam, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.
jeevikaruna2000@gmail.com

Received: 22nd Oct 2025 / Accepted : 29th Oct 2025 ,
© ICIAET 2025

Abstract

Cleft lip and palate (CLP) are congenital deformities affecting the lip, palate, or both, occurring due to disruption in facial fusion during the 4th to 12th week of gestation. Globally, CLP affects 1 in every 700 births; in India, over 35,000 children are born with CLP annually. In Tamil Nadu, the prevalence is 1 in 529 live births and 1 in 770 in Chennai. The condition is more common in male children, though isolated cleft palate is more frequent in females. The aim of the study is to improve hunger satisfaction and anthropometric measurements among infants with cleft lip and cleft palate. A quasi-experimental study was conducted at Saveetha Medical College and Hospital, Chennai, to assess the effectiveness of an alternative feeding method (Pigeon cleft bottle) on hunger satisfaction and anthropometric measurements among CLP infants. A total of 60 infants were selected using a convenience sampling method—30 in the experimental group and 30 in the control group. Baseline hunger satiety and

anthropometric data were recorded, followed by a one-week intervention using the alternative feeding method for the experimental group. The control group continued with the routine feeding practice. Post-test data were collected and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results showed a significant improvement in hunger satisfaction in the experimental group, with mean scores increasing from 3.73 (SD 1.39) to 5.97 (SD 0.81). Anthropometric data showed improvement, though not statistically significant. No association was found between demographic variables and post-test hunger satisfaction.

Keywords: cleft lip and cleft palate, alternative feeding method, hunger satisfaction, anthropometric measurements.

INTRODUCTION:

Cleft lip and palate (CLP) are congenital malformations that can affect the lip, the palate, or both, resulting from errors in the embryonic facial

fusion process due to alterations in the normal development of the primary and/or secondary palate in the 4th to 12th week of pregnancy. With the diagnosis of cleft palate/lip, feeding is a major concern for parents. Feeding difficulties appear at birth, due to impairment of the sucking and swallowing mechanisms resulting from the alteration in the anatomical structures. At this early stage, the priority is monitoring infant nutrition and weight gain.

Cleft affected infants often face major challenges are insufficient sucking, gasping, nasal regurgitation, difficulty gaining weight, chronic ear infections and hearing loss, speech and language delay, dental problems, social and psychological challenges and the minor challenges are prolonged feeding times, excessive air intake. While genetic predisposition on chromosome 8 is more common in people with cleft lip and palate is a significant factor and other contributors include poor maternal nutrition, tobacco use, alcohol consumption, and obesity during pregnancy, smoking during pregnancy, diabetes, advanced maternal age, and the use of certain medications, such as Antiepileptic and anti-cancer drugs.

The Pigeon Cleft Palate Soft Bottle and Medela Special Needs Feeder which comprise a one-way valve and a squeezable bottle are among the commonly used bottles for children with CLP. With these bottles, it is possible to feed the infant by compressing the nipple or bottle without the child having to generate negative intraoral pressure. The Pigeon bottle feeder with a long, soft, and thin nipple (hereafter referred to as Long Nipple) has a special shape and is less expensive than other nipples. The objective of the study is to improve hunger satisfaction and anthropometric measurements among infants with cleft lip and cleft palate.

Molina-Solana et.al. (2019) a study on environmental factors in study indicates that in cleft lip and/or palate main factors. Aim of this study was to investigate the effect of environmental factors, such as tobacco, alcohol and folic acid intake, obesity, stressful events, low blood levels of zinc and fever during pregnancy, on the incidence

of cleft lip and/or palate. On the findings of this study tobacco 1.48, alcohol 1.28, folic acid intake 0.77, obesity 1.26, stressful events 1.41, low blood zinc levels 1.82 and fever during pregnancy 1.30. **Ashwinirani S. et al. (2022)** studied 80 cleft lip and palate (CLP) patients, finding UCLP most common (46.2%), followed by BCLP (35%) and CL alone (18.8%). CLP was more frequent in males, with left-side dominance. Key predisposing factors included advanced maternal age (62.5%) and consanguineous marriage (40%).

METHODS AND MATERIALS:

A Quantitative research approach with quasi experimental study was conducted to assess the effectiveness of alternative feeding method on hunger satisfaction and anthropometric measurements among Infants with cleft lip and cleft palate. The main study was conducted in pediatric ward at Saveetha Medical College and Hospital, Chennai. A total of 60 samples who met the inclusion criteria were selected by convenience sampling technique. 30 samples in experimental group and 30 samples in control group. The investigator introduced her and explained the purpose of the study to the mothers. Informed consent was obtained from mothers and confidentiality was assured. Assessed the hunger satiety scale and anthropometric measurements and pigeon cleft feeding method was provided to the experimental group and control group was followed the routine feeding method as followed by the mother. After that in post- test assessed the hunger satiety and anthropometric measurements for the infants. Data were analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistics.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

SECTION A: Description of the demographic variables of the cleft lip and cleft palate infants.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of demographic variables of cleft lip and cleft palate infants.

Most infants in the experimental (63.33%) and control (56.67%) groups were aged 10–12 months.

ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ALTERNATIVE FEEDING METHOD ON HUNGER SATISFACTION AND ANTHROPOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS AMONG INFANTS WITH CLEFT LIP AND CLEFT PALATE AT SAVEETHA MEDICAL COLLEGE AND HOSPITAL AT CHENNAI

Females predominated in the experimental group (53.33%), while males were more in the control group (53.33%). A majority weighed 3–3.5 kg (70.00% and 66.67%). Cleft palate was common (50.00% experimental, 53.33% control), followed by cleft lip. No family history was noted. Bottle-feeding was prevalent (80.00% and 83.33%), with some using paladai or cup and spoon. Sucking difficulties were most reported, along with choking. Most infants (80.00% experimental, 70.00% control) urinated 6–8 times daily, suggesting adequate hydration.

SECTION B: Frequency and percentage distribution of level of hunger satisfaction in the experimental group and control group.

Level of hunger satisfaction	Experimental group				Control group		P value
	Pre-test		Post-test		Pre-test		
	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Extremely hungry	2	6.67	0	0.00	5	16.67	0.001
Hungry	23	76.67	0	0.00	19	63.33	0.002
Neutral to slightly satisfied	5	16.67	21	70.00	6	20.00	0.008
Full to very full (comfortably satisfied)	0	0.00	9	30.00	0	0.00	0.000
Overfull to stuffed	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0.000

Table 2 shows that experimental group, before the intervention, most infants (76.67%) were hungry, 6.67% were extremely hungry, and 16.67% were slightly satisfied. None were full. After the intervention, hunger levels improved greatly 70% were slightly satisfied, and 30% were full. No infants were hungry or extremely hungry. In the control group, there was little change. Before the test, 63.33% were hungry, 16.67% extremely hungry, and 20% slightly satisfied. After the test,

66.67% were still hungry, 6.67% extremely hungry, and only 26.67% were slightly satisfied. None reached the full level.

Percentage distribution of pre-test and post-test levels of hunger satisfaction in the experimental group

SECTION C: Comparison of level of effectiveness of alternative feeding method on hunger satisfaction and anthropometric measurements between experimental group and control group.

Table 3: Comparison of level of effectiveness of alternative feeding method on hunger satisfaction between experimental group and control group.

Level of hunger satisfaction	Experimental group		Control group	
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D
Pre-test	3.73	1.39	3.57	1.55
Post-test	5.97	0.81	3.83	1.44
Mean difference score	2.23		0.27	
Paired t test & p value	t= 7.3942 p<0.001 **		t= 1.7647 p= 0.0881	

NOTE:

p<0.001 **
- Highly significant

p<0.05 *- Significant

p>0.05- Not significant

ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ALTERNATIVE FEEDING METHOD ON HUNGER SATISFACTION AND ANTHROPOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS AMONG INFANTS WITH CLEFT LIP AND CLEFT PALATE AT SAVEETHA MEDICAL COLLEGE AND HOSPITAL AT CHENNAI

Table 3 shows that the pre-test phase, the mean hunger satisfaction score for the experimental group was 3.73 with a standard deviation (SD) of 1.39, while the control group had a mean score of 3.57 with an SD of 1.55.

In the post-test, the experimental group showed a marked improvement with a mean score of 5.97 (SD = 0.81), whereas the control group recorded a mean score of 3.83 (SD = 1.44).

The within-group comparison using the paired t-test also showed a statistically significant increase in the experimental group ($t = 7.3942, p < 0.001$), while the change in the control group was not statistically significant ($t = 1.7647, p = 0.0881$).

Boxplot showing level of effectiveness of alternative feeding method on hunger satisfaction between the experimental group and control group

Table 4: Comparison of level of effectiveness of alternative feeding method on anthropometric measurements between experimental group and control group.

Parameter	Experimental group				p-value (ANOVA)
	Day 1 Mean score	Day 2 Mean score	Day 3 Mean score	1 Week Mean score	
Weight (kg)	7.792	7.842	7.891	7.942	0.9951

Height (cm)	68.083	68.383	68.683	68.983	0.9870
Head Circumference	42.55	42.75	42.95	43.15	0.9693
Chest Circumference	43.323	43.523	43.723	43.923	0.9804

Parameter	Control group				p-value (ANOVA)
	Day 1 Mean score	Day 2 Mean score	Day 3 Mean score	1 Week Mean score	
Weight (kg)	7.706	7.706	7.763	8.02	0.9317
Height (cm)	69.566	69.567	69.567	70.566	0.9164
Head Circumference	44.626	44.626	44.626	44.967±2.17	0.9034
Chest Circumference	45.073	45.073	45.073	45.723±3.74	0.8701

Table 4 shows that there was a gradual and consistent increase observed in all anthropometric parameters over time. The mean weight rose from 7.792 kg on Day 1 to 7.942 kg after 1 week. Similarly, height increased from 68.083 cm to 68.983 cm. A steady improvement was also noted in head circumference (from 42.55 cm to 43.15 cm) and chest circumference (from 43.323 cm to 43.923 cm).

SECTION D: Association of post-test level of effectiveness of alternative feeding method on hunger satisfaction and anthropometric measurements among the cleft lip and cleft palate infants with selected demographic variables in the experimental group.

ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ALTERNATIVE FEEDING METHOD ON HUNGER SATISFACTION AND ANTHROPOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS AMONG INFANTS WITH CLEFT LIP AND CLEFT PALATE AT SAVEETHA MEDICAL COLLEGE AND HOSPITAL AT CHENNAI

Demographic variables	Experimental group	
	Frequency	Chi square and p value
Age in months		
0-3 Months	7	$\chi^2 = 1.6911$ d.f= 3 p= 0.6389 Not significant
4-6 Months	3	
7-9 Months	1	
10-12 Months	19	
Gender		
Male	14	$\chi^2 = 0.0255$ d.f= 1 p= 0.8731 Not significant
Female	16	
Birth weight		
3 to 3.5kg	21	$\chi^2 = 0.0680$ d.f= 1 p= 0.7942 Not significant
2.5 to 3kg	9	
2 to 2.5kg	0	
Type of cleft		
Cleft lip	9	$\chi^2 = 1.4815$ d.f= 2 p= 0.4768 Not significant
Cleft palate	15	
Both	6	
Siblings with any cleft lip and cleft palate in family history		
Yes	0	-
No	30	
Feeding method adopted at present		
Bottle feeding	24	$\chi^2 = 0.6746$ d.f= 2 p= 0.7137 Not significant
Filler	0	
Cup and spoon feeding	1	
Paaladai feeding	5	

Challenges faced during feeding		
Poor latch	0	$\chi^2 = 1.1230$ d.f= 2 p= 0.5704 Not significant
Difficulty sucking	17	
Choking/ aspiration	11	
None of the above	2	
How often baby urinate a day		
4-6 times	2	$\chi^2 = 1.0317$ d.f= 2 p= 0.5970 Not significant
6-8 times	24	
Less than 4 times	0	
More than 8 times	4	

Table-5 reveals that all the demographic variables of cleft lip and cleft palate infants do not show a statistical significance with the level of effectiveness of alternative feeding method on hunger satisfaction in the experimental group, except the factor, age in months ($\chi^2 = 14.8456$, $p = 0.0215$), all the other variables do not show any statistical significance with the level of effectiveness of alternative feeding method on hunger satisfaction. Hence, we conclude the demographic variables of cleft lip and cleft palate infants has no significant influence with respect to the level of effectiveness of alternative feeding method on hunger satisfaction in the experimental group, except, age in months.

CONCLUSION:

The study concluded that the alternative feeding method was effective in improving hunger satisfaction and anthropometric measurements among infants with cleft lip and cleft palate. Infants in the experimental group showed noticeable improvement in feeding responses, with reduced hunger levels post-intervention compared to the control group. Additionally, there was a positive trend in weight gain and other anthropometric parameters, indicating better nutritional intake and

growth. These findings suggest that alternative feeding methods can significantly enhance feeding efficiency, reduce complications like choking or aspiration, and promote overall health and development in affected infants and further research may comparing different types of alternative feeding methods (e.g., paladai, squeezable bottles, specialty feeders) may provide more detailed insights into the most effective options.

Acknowledgement: author would like to appreciate all the study participant and mothers for their co-operation to complete the study successfully.

References:

1. Becker de Oliveira, L., et al. (2023). Breastfeeding and cleft lip and palate: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Cleft Palate-Craniofacial Journal*, 60(10), 1344–1355. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10556656231165685>
2. Chandrasekhar, A., et al. (2019). Cup with spoon feeding in cleft infants. *Journal of Cleft Lip Palate and Craniofacial Anomalies*, 6(1), 14–25.
3. Dash, M., et al. (2023). Feeding interventions among cleft lip/palate infants: A systematic review and meta-synthesis. *Journal of Cleft Lip Palate and Craniofacial Anomalies*, 10(1), 14–25.
4. Doneria, D., et al. (2025). Knowledge, attitudes, and practices of dentists of different specialties regarding nasoalveolar molding in patients with cleft lip and palate: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Cleft Lip Palate and Craniofacial Anomalies*, 12(1), 3–8.
5. Putri, F. A., et al. (2024). The global occurrences of cleft lip and palate in pediatric patients and their association with demographic factors: A narrative review.
6. Hlongwa, P., et al. (2019). Epidemiology and clinical profile of individuals with cleft lip and palate utilising specialised academic treatment centres in South Africa. *PLOS ONE*, 14(3), e0212611. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0212611>
7. Martin, A., et al. (2024). Evaluation of factors influencing feeding in babies with a cleft palate with and without a cleft lip. *Journal of Child Health Care*, 28(1), 72–83.
8. Heydari, M., et al. (2022). Global prevalence of cleft palate, cleft lip, and cleft lip and palate: A comprehensive systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Stomatology, Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery*, 123(2), 110–120.
9. Ravi, D., et al. (2019). Weight gain pattern of infants with orofacial cleft on three types of feeding techniques. *Indian Journal of Pediatrics*, 86(7), 581–585.
10. Reina, S., et al. (2023). Population prevalence and trends of oral clefts in Colombia: A prevalence study. *The Cleft Palate-Craniofacial Journal*, 60(6), 716–723.
11. Saheeb, B. D., et al. (2021). Comparison of weight gain in newborns with different feeding methods. *Journal of Cleft Lip Palate and Craniofacial Anomalies*, 8(1), 14–25.
12. Salari, N., et al. (2022). Global prevalence of cleft palate, cleft lip, and cleft lip and palate: A comprehensive systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Stomatology, Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery*, 123(2), 110–120.
13. Sundoro, A., et al. (2021). Corrective procedures for children with orofacial clefts.
14. Rikima, S., et al. (2022). Molecular contribution to cleft palate production in cleft lip mice. *Congenital Anomalies (Kyoto)*, 62(2), 94–99.
15. Ulucan, F., et al. (2019). Prevalence of cleft lip and cleft palate. *Santosh University Journal of Health Sciences*, 5(4), 200–203.

16. Yow, M., Jin, A., & Yeo, G. S. H. (n.d).
Epidemiologic trends of infants with orofacial clefts in a multiethnic country: A retrospective population-based study.
17. Jiang, Y., et al. (2023). Incidence of cleft lip and palate and epidemiology of perinatal deaths related to cleft lip and palate in Hunan Province, China., 103–105.